

GLASS MATRIX COMPOSITES-II-ALUMINA REINFORCED GLASS

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An all ceramic composite system comprised of high strength alumina fibers in a glass matrix is described. The concept for this type of composite arose from the recent availability of alumina fiber from DuPont Corporation in tow form with individual fiber diameters of twenty microns, a reasonably high strength (2170 MPa), high elastic modulus (395 GPa) and a possible future low cost. Calculations of the microstresses in the alumina-fiber reinforced glass matrix as the composite is thermally cycled indicate that the structural integrity of the composite is maintained even after repeated heating to temperatures of 1000°C or higher for alumina fibers in a silica matrix and temperatures of 540°C for alumina fibers in a borosilicate glass matrix. Several methods of fabricating such an alumina fiber-glass matrix composite were considered and the slurry method originally adapted by Levitt (1) for his work on graphite fiber-glass matrix composites was adopted.

The preparation of these composites is described in detail and the effects of the processing parameters on the microstructure of the matrix, the mechanical and dielectric properties, and the thermal shock resistance of the material is noted. The first part of the paper is concerned only with uniaxial composites of alumina fiber in borosilicate or aluminosilicate glasses and the second part of the paper is based on the properties of biaxial composites of alumina fiber in silica or in silica slightly diluted with a borosilicate glass as a liquid phase sintering aid. The retention of strength by the composite as a function of temperature, the thermal conductivity of the biaxial composites, and the coefficient of linear expansion have been measured and are included in the paper.

At this stage of research, i.e. at the end of two years work, the properties of the alumina fiber reinforced glass composite may be summarized by saying that it has seven times the flexural strength of impregnated slip cast fused silica, a low dielectric constant and loss tangent, a moderately low (c.f. to ceramics) coefficient of linear expansion, a low thermal conductivity, an excellent thermal shock resistance, and, of course, fine environmental stability up to temperatures of at least 1100°C. Based on the results of

differential thermal analysis no reaction is found between the alumina fiber and the silica matrix up to the maximum temperature (1440°C) employed in the hot-pressing procedures to date. Future investigations are necessary to decide whether these composites can also be readily formed by hot isostatic pressing, a procedure which should both allow the formation of a number of composite objects at one time as well as permit the making of bigger shapes than are now possible by the conventional hot pressing procedures of this paper. The basic research of this program has been made possible by a contract with the Air Force Materials Laboratory of Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Dayton, Ohio, with Mr. Donald Evans as contract monitor. This work continues with emphasis on increased strength.

Introduction

Fiber reinforced composites are widely accepted as structural materials because of their special attributes of high strength, high moduli and low density. However, even the best of these composites such as a carbon or boron or glass fiber reinforced organic matrix is limited in use to temperatures below 300°C. Substitutions of an aluminum alloy as the matrix improves the temperature limitations only slightly. If one thinks of glass as a high temperature polymer then a fiber reinforced glass or fused silica suggests itself as a promising composite for medium and high temperature applications. Despite this fact only a handful of references occur in the literature on the subject of fiber reinforced glass or ceramic matrix composites and the most pertinent of these to the present investigation is the work by Levitt (1).

Levitt developed graphite fiber reinforced composites where the matrix composition was $\text{Li}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot n\text{SiO}_2$ with $n = 3, 4$ and 8 . He used a drum winding apparatus to produce graphite fiber/ceramic matrix tapes which were then hot pressed to their final dimensions. He obtained fivefold increases in modulus of rupture with no fall-off after repeated thermal cycling to 1200°C. His composites were generally characterized by low porosity, intimate fiber-matrix contact and an uncracked matrix, which was the result of a suitable thermal expansion match between fiber and matrix and the formulation of a strong fiber-matrix bond. Izod impact energies of 20 to 30 ft-lb/in² for the notched specimens and 75 ft-lb/in² for the unnotched specimens were obtained at room temperature. At about the time this research was proposed, low-cost alumina fiber appeared on the market so that the idea of investigating an alumina fiber reinforced glass matrix composite suggested itself particularly since such composites would be insulators with low dielectric constant.

Micromechanical Behavior of a Fiber in a Surrounding Matrix

In view of the large temperature drop from the softening temperature range of the proposed matrix materials to the minimum service temperature and the requirement to prevent matrix cracking under the residual stresses, C. H. Wells, then at UTRC and now at Southwest Research Institute, made a detailed calculation of the thermal expansion of a single ply, the average elastic properties and the residual microstresses for the two fiber-matrix combinations. An approximate model, indicated in Figure 1, was used for these estimates which were primarily intended to evaluate the feasibility of the alumina fiber-glass

Fig. 1 - Fiber Matrix Geometry

matrix composite. In this model each fiber is assumed to be bonded to an equivalent cylindrical shell of matrix and to be stress free at the softening temperature of the matrix. The radius of the cylindrical shell was taken as one-half of the fiber spacing in an equivalent triangular array, neglecting the area of matrix bounded by the three tangent circles of Figure 1. The area fraction of matrix in the case of equal volumes of fiber and matrix is 10% lower than the true value, i.e. 0.45 instead of 0.50, which was considered sufficiently accurate for the purpose.

The fiber-matrix interfacial pressure, p , the tangential stress in the matrix and the axial stresses in the fiber and matrix were determined from the Lamé solution for a thick-walled cylinder under internal pressure. The total, elastic plus thermal, strains in the fiber and matrix were matched in the axial and circumferential directions. The matrix thermal expansion was assumed isotropic, but the fibers were assumed to have two different coefficients of expansion in the radial and axial directions. Because Poisson's ratio was not available for the alumina fiber, the value of 0.20 was assumed. Consequently, the interfacial pressure was independent of axial loading. Equating the total axial and circumferential strains and assuming the composite is cooled through a temperature range of 1000°C , the Lamé equations gave the results for the residual microstresses which are summarized in Table I.

Table I. Calculated Microstresses

	DuPont Alumina Fibers in Pyrex *	DuPont Alumina Fibers in Silica
Interfacial pressure -P ksi	-14,500	-18,600
Circumferential matrix stress $\sigma_{\theta m}$ ksi	-43,500	-55,800
Longitudinal matrix stress σ_{zm} ksi	-39,100	-51,200
Longitudinal fiber stress σ_{zf} ksi	+39,100	+51,200

*Registered trade-mark, Corning Glass Works, Corning, N.Y.

The combination of either DuPont alumina fibers Type FP in borosilicate glass or in fused silica appear acceptable and combined with the results found by Levitt, the alumina fiber reinforced glass program looked promising especially since in all cases the glass matrix is in compression thus fully utilizing the very high compressive strength of this material.

Choice of the Particular Alumina Fibers
and Glasses for this Program

The several alumina fibers and glasses considered for this research are shown in Table II. The DuPont alumina fiber, Type FP, was chosen in contrast to the somewhat similar 3M alumina fiber because of its higher modulus. This DuPont fiber in the manner in which it arrives at the purchaser is shown in Figure 2. The fibers themselves are 20 micron diameter round continuous fibers with a density of 3.95 gms/cm, an average strength of 1720 MPa or 250 ksi, and a Young's modulus of 345 GPa or 50 million psi. As shown in Figure 2, the DuPont alumina fiber is supplied in yarn form wound on spools and having approximately 200 fibers to the tow. The result of measuring the strength of 24 individual DuPont alumina fiber Type FP fibers is shown in Figure 3 where the low strength values are primarily due to kinks in the fiber. This DuPont fiber has outstanding ability to retain its strength on long exposures in air at temperatures at least as high as 1000°C in contrast to rival fibers such as boron or silicon carbide coated boron fibers as shown in Figure 4. The manner in which the DuPont fiber retains its modulus as a function of temperature is shown in Figure 5 where only a minor decrease in modulus occurs even at temperatures above 900°C.

Table II. Physical Characteristics of Several
Reinforcing Fibers and Matrices

MATERIAL	DENSITY gms/cm ³	COEFFICIENT OF LINEAR EXPANSION 10 ⁻⁷ per °C	MODULUS 10 ⁶ psi	SPECIFIC MODULUS 10 ⁷ in.	STRENGTH 10 ³ psi	SPECIFIC STRENGTH 10 ⁶
CORNING 7971 LOW EXP GLASS	2.205	-0.3	6.9	-	-	-
CORNING 7940 FUSED SILICA	2.205	3.3	10.0	-	-	-
SILICON NITRIDE HOT PRESSED	2.8	32	31	-	-	-
CORNING 7740 BOROSILICATE GLASS	2.23	32.5	6.4	-	-	-
CORNING 1723 ALUMINO-SILICA FIBERS & GLASS	2.64	46	8.9	-	-	-
CORNING 9606 PYROCERAM	2.6	57	12	-	-	-
ALUMINA FIBER 3M	2.7	63	23	23.7	250	2.58
ALUMINA FIBER DUPONT	3.1	74	50	35.0	250	1.76
COORS ALUMINA AD199	3.96	63	50		35	
BORON NITRIDE FIBERS CARBON - DUM CONTRACT	2.0	102 ALONG FIBER 6 ACROSS FIBER	33.8	46.8	236	3.27
UARL GLASS FIBER 417	3.09	51.7	18.4	16.5	772	6.92

Fig. 2 - DuPont Alumina Fiber As Purchased

Fig. 3 - Distribution of Strength of Individual Al_2O_3 Fibers-DuPont FP

Fig. 4 - Fiber Tensile Strength Retention After Exposure to Temperature in Air

To make the proposed alumina fiber reinforced glass matrix a large number of glasses are readily available as shown in Table II since the only essential requirement is that the glass must have a smaller coefficient of thermal expansion than the relatively large coefficient of expansion of the alumina fiber, 74×10^{-7} cm/cm per $^{\circ}C$. On this basis five glasses were selected for this investigation, Corning Glass Works 7740 or Pyrex*, C.G.W. 1723 - an aluminosilicate glass, C.G.W. 7913 or Vycor*, C.G.W. 7940 or fused silica, and the Ferro "S" glass. These glasses have coefficients of expansion 32.5, 40, 5.5, 3.9 and 60×10^{-7} cm/cm $^{\circ}C$ respectively. They all have Young's moduli of approximately 9 to 12 million psi and flexural strengths in the abraded bulk

Fig. 5 - Fiber Elastic Modulus As A Function of Temperature

condition of 6000 to 7000 psi. The glasses are purchased as fine powders of 90% through 325 mesh as shown in Figure 6 where it can be seen that these powders also contain numerous fines of 1 micron or less in size. The very great differences in these glasses even though they are all relatively low-expansion glasses is shown in Figure 7 where the viscosity of the glass is plotted as a function of temperature. Since these glasses respond to hot pressing only at temperatures between the softening point and working point it is evident that pure fused silica or even the Vycor require extremely high hot pressing temperatures at which temperatures the alumina fiber will suffer deterioration. The necessity for these extreme temperatures, however, can be ameliorated by diluting the high temperature glass with a few percent of a lower temperature glass such as Pyrex.

Method of Making the Composite

Several methods exist for making fiber reinforced glass matrix composites and, indeed, in the preliminary evaluation studies UTRC considered as many as six different processes. The simplest and lowest cost method, if it can be made to work consistently, consists of pulling the alumina fiber tow through

Fig. 6 - Glass Powders

*Registered trademark, Corning Glass Works, Corning, NY

a slurry containing a suspension of the finely ground glass particles.

In the slurry process for coating the alumina fiber with glass, the alumina fiber is unwound from the spool and pulled through an agitated organic solution containing a suspension of fine glass particles of that special glass chosen for the matrix. The process is shown schematically in Figure 8. In greater detail, the continuous alumina tow is unwound from the spool on which it is received at a moderate rate of speed, pulled through a slip comprised of powdered glass, solvent and plasticizer to impregnate the tow, and rewound

Fig. 7 - Viscosity vs Temperature for Several Glasses

Fig. 8 - Slurry Method of Coating Alumina Fiber

onto a large rotating drum covered with mylar tape to prevent sticking of the impregnated alumina fiber. The slip may be composed of 40 grams of powdered glass and 3 grams of polyvinyl alcohol dissolved in 100 grams of water to which 2 grams of ethylene glycol is added as a plasticizer. Alternately, the slip may comprise 85 grams of glass in 225 ml of toluene to which 5 grams of polystyrene and 5 drops of tergitol have been added. The large drum is run at one revolution per minute or a linear speed of 5 ft/min. Excess glass and solvent are removed by pressing a squeegee against the drum as it winds.

After the tape is dry (sometimes heating with a radiant heat source is necessary to speed up the removal of excess solvent) it is cut and removed from the drum and then further cut into strips or squares the size of the die to be used for hot pressing. It is then layed up in the die to give unidirectional or cross plied fiber alignments and hot pressed. The hot pressing may be carried out in vacuum using metal or graphite dies coated with colloidal boron nitride at pressures of 2000 to 3000 psi and temperatures of 1050 to

1200°C for the common borosilicate glass. Alternately, the hot pressing operation can also be carried out in argon using again graphite dies sprayed with boron nitride powder.

Process Variables

There are obviously many variables in the process just described. For example, the amount of glass in the slurry, the rate at which the fiber is pulled through the slurry, the particular organic constituents chosen, the amount of agitation that is used to keep the slurry well mixed, the composition of the slurry at the beginning and end of the process. While all of these variables are important, they can both be compensated for and controlled by determining the relative amounts of glass and alumina fiber in the tape. If too little glass has been picked up by the fiber it can be corrected by adding weighed packets of glass during the lay-up process. This is especially true since during the hot pressing process the glass moves readily into the tows and throughout the composite.

The variables during hot pressing such as temperature, pressure and atmosphere are much more important and these have been studied extensively. The results can best be understood by examining Figure 9 which gives the flexural strength of the alumina fiber-glass matrix composite as both a function of hot-pressing temperature and of atmosphere. As the data plotted in Figure 9 show there is a sharply defined optimum temperature for the hot-pressed sample to have maximum flexural strength and this temperature is different in an argon atmosphere compared to a vacuum atmosphere presumably because of the difference in the thermal conductivity of these two atmospheres. All of the data of Figure 9 were obtained by hot pressing at a pressure of 2000 psi which has proven to be slightly the best for this operation.

Fig. 9 - Effect of Hot Pressing Temperature on 3 Point Flexural Strength

Experimental Results

Uniaxial Composites of DuPont Alumina Fiber Type FP in Borosilicate or Aluminosilicate Glass Matrices

As will be shown in the next paragraph, the microstructure of an alumina fiber reinforced glass matrix is very uniform and, accordingly, not much scatter in results if nine specimens are cut from a given hot pressed sample and the three-point flexural strength of each determined. In Table III the results of measurement of the three-point flexural strength of nine specimens

Table III. 3 Point Flexural Strength of DuPont Alumina Fiber FP-C.G.W. 1723 Glass Composition

Position	Strength (ksi)	MPa	Position	Strength (ksi)	MPa
L1	33.71	232	C3	41.40	286
L2	38.07	263	R1	48.08	332
L3	31.93	220	R2	50.87	351
C1	44.25	305	R3	39.19	270
C2	34.29	237	Avg	40.2	

cut from the same sample of hot pressed DuPont alumina fiber, Type FP, in a C.G.W. Code 1723 glass matrix (an aluminosilicate glass matrix). The results vary from 31.90 ksi or 220 MPa to 48.08 ksi or 332 MPa with an average of 40.2 ksi or 277 MPa. It will also be seen that there is no relation to position in the sample with the result obtained for the specimen cut from that position. Similar results are shown in Figure 10 where the three-point flexural strength of eight specimens cut from the same sample of DuPont alumina fiber, Type FP, in a Ferro "S" glass matrix are plotted on probability paper. The relatively small spread of results obtained for these specimens of a brittle fiber in a brittle matrix is again evident. The average flexural strength for this sample of alumina fiber reinforced Ferro "S" glass matrix is about the same as that for the alumina fiber reinforced C.G.W. aluminosilica glass matrix showing the strength of the specimen is not greatly affected by the choice of glass when both glasses have about the same working temperatures. The small spread of values in the strengths of these glass composites enables the designer to use the results with confidence and the approximate linear character of the results shown in Figure 10 confirm the Gaussian distribution of the results. Measurement of the elastic modulus for these composites gives a result of approximately 152 GPa or 22 million psi and using the rule of mixtures this would indicate a fiber content of approximately 30%. If this figure of 30% fiber by volume is used to calculate the expected strength of the composites by the rule of mixtures a value of 544 MPa or 79 ksi is found in place of the experimental values just shown of 277 MPa or 40.2 ksi, and it is felt that this lower value results from the very strong chemical bonding between the alumina fiber and the glass matrix.

How does the experimental value of 277 MPa or 40.2 ksi flexural strength

Fig. 10 - Cumulative Probability of Failure of FP Al₂O₃ Fiber - "S" Glass Composites

for the alumina fiber reinforced glass matrix composite compare with measured results of three-point flexural strengths of refractories intended for similar use? In Table IV data are shown for high quality alumina, beryllia, fused silica refractories and Pyroceram* 9606 in comparison with the alumina fiber reinforced glass matrix composite. It can be seen that the DuPont alumina fiber, Type FP, reinforced aluminosilicate or borosilicate glass matrix composite has approximately six times the flexural strength of fused silica, twice the flexural strength of C.G.W. Pyroceram 9606 and is slightly better than a good beryllia refractory and nearly equally to a high grade alumina refractory.

Table IV. Achieved Strength of Al_2O_3 Fiber Reinforced Glass Matrix Composites

Material	Density gms/cm ³	Percent major phase	Flexural strength (ksi)	Young's modulus 10 ⁶ psi
Alumina	3.9	99.5	45	52
Beryllia	2.95	>99	35	50
Fused silica	2.2	99.9	7	10.5
FerroS- Al_2O_3 fiber	2.92	30 fiber 70 glass	42.7	25.3

In Figure 11 there is shown an optical tape-map of a complete cross-section of a recently made specimen of an alumina fiber reinforced glass matrix composite taken at a magnification of 50 diameters. The great uniformity and high fiber density (approximately 60% by volume) is evident. When a similar sample of this alumina fiber reinforced glass matrix composite is fractured it breaks in a brittle-brittle manner as judged by the scanning electron micrograph of Figure 12. This micrograph emphasizes that on fracture the glass breaks away from the alumina fiber and leaves short lengths of alumina fiber protruding. The same figure also shows that no fiber seems to touch any other fiber and that each fiber is surrounded by glass.

Fig. 11 - Optical Tape Map of Recent Specimen of DuPont FP Fiber in C.G.W. 1723 Composite

200 μ

In this discussion of the results obtained with uniaxial specimens of alumina fiber reinforced borosilicate or aluminosilicate glass matrices no mention has yet been made of the dielectric constant of such specimens. In

*Registered trademark, Corning Glass Works, Corning, NY

Fig. 12 - Scanning Electron Micrograph of Fracture Surface of LB 41-1

Table V the results of measuring the dielectric constants six specimens of alumina fiber reinforced glass matrices are compared with a similar measurement of C.G.W. Pyroceram 9606. The data indicate that if only low molecular weight highly volatile materials such as isopropyl alcohol are used as the organic constituents of the slurry through which the alumina fiber is pulled, then the alumina fiber reinforced glass matrix composite has an acceptably low dielectric and loss tangent. On the other, the addition of any higher molecular weight loss volatile organic constituent such as polyvinyl alcohol or polystyrene to the slurry gives a composite with an unacceptably high dielectric constant presumably because the residue of such materials remains behind as a carbonaceous char in the hot-pressed specimen.

Table V. Effect of Process on Dielectric Constant

<u>Process (7740 glass in all cases)</u>	<u>Dielectric constant</u>	<u>Tan δ</u>
Hot pressed glass only, no slurry, fiber on surface	4.80	0.0070
Hot pressed glass, alumina fiber, isopropyl alcohol	6.05	0.0201
Hot pressed glass plus bare alumina fiber	6.65	0.0104
Hot pressed glass, isopropyl and polyvinyl alcohols, and alumina fiber	7.92	0.110
Hot pressed glass, alumina fiber, isopropyl and polyvinyl alcohols, and polystyrene	8.05	0.194
Corning 9606 commercial Pyroceram	5.65	0.002

Uniaxial Composites of DuPont Alumina Fiber Type FP in a Fused Silica Matrix

In all of the earlier work, alumina fiber reinforced glass composites were prepared by pulling the bundle of DuPont alumina fiber, Type FP, through a slurry of powdered glass in isopropyl alcohol with 5 drops of a wetting agent added and in addition various organic "glues" such as polyvinyl alcohol or polystyrene. This technique gave problems inasmuch as it was difficult to remove all of the organic binders and any remnant left a char in the composite which gave it too high a dielectric constant. The same technique was also subject to other difficulties since the tape did not pick up enough glass and additional glass had to be added between the layers in weighed amounts to arrive at the desired composition of the composite. Further, during the lay-

ing up process the tape would shed powdered glass in uncontrollable amounts and finally the tapes lacked "green" strength. A new process in which the DuPont alumina fiber, Type FP, is pulled through a slurry composed of uniform aqueous colloidal dispersion of spherical particles of silica in an alkaline media* eliminates all of the difficulties encountered with the organic slurry just described. In this slurry the alkaline media reacts with the silica surface to produce a negative charge and to keep the silica particles in colloidal suspension. Added powdered silica or Pyrex glass may be added to the suspension to give the fiber content desired.

Table VI. Strength of FP Al₂O₃ Reinforced Silica Matrix

Fused SiO ₂ matrix (37% vol. approx. fiber)		
Sample	Three-point flexural strength	
	MPa	kpsi
LB368 RB	163	23.6
TR	224	32.4
BC	177	25.7
TC	190	27.5
LB	185	26.8
TL	185	26.8
Mean	187	27.1
Stand. dev.	20	2.92
Stand. err.	8.2	1.19

The three-point flexural strength of an Al₂O₃ fiber reinforced fused silica matrix is given in Table VI for a composite with only 37% Al₂O₃ fiber content. The data again show a high degree of consistency not normally to be expected for this type of brittle-brittle composite with a standard deviation of only 2.92 kpsi or 20 MPa. The low flexural strength found is to be expected for a composite with this low (37% by volume) of alumina fiber as may be seen by comparison with Figure 13 where the trend of bending strength as a function of alumina fiber content (by volume) is shown for 16 different alumina reinforced fused silica composites. If UTRC can achieve a fiber content of 60% by volume in the fused silica composites, it is expected that the bending strength will be approximately 40 to 42 kpsi (276 to 290 MPa) and exactly the

Fig. 13 - Strength of FP Al₂O₃ Reinforced Silica Matrix as a Function of Al₂O₃ Content

*DuPont Ludox HS 30%

Fig. 14 - Strength of FP Al_2O_3 Reinforced Silica Matrix at Several Temperatures

same as for the alumina fiber reinforced borosilicate and aluminosilicate glass matrices. The ability of the alumina fiber reinforced fused silica (5% dilution with Pyrex) glass matrix to retain its strength as the temperature is increased is shown in Figure 14 from room temperature to 1000°C. Figure 15 shows an optical tape-map of a section of alumina fiber reinforced fused silica (5% Pyrex added) and in contrast to the optical tape-map shown in Figure 11 for the alumina fiber reinforced aluminosilicate glass the lower density and the more irregular distribution of alumina fiber is immediately apparent. Figure 16 shows several micrographs of alumina fiber reinforced fused silica (5% Pyrex addition) and again confirms the lower content of fiber in these composites together with its less regular distribution.

Fig. 15 - Tape-Map of FP Al_2O_3 Fiber Reinforced SiO_2

Fig. 16 - Several Micrographs of Al_2O_3 Fiber Reinforced Silica Composites

Biaxial Specimens of DuPont Alumina Fiber, Type FP, in Glass or Silica Matrix

The first biaxial samples consisted of composites of approximately 50% (by volume) alumina fiber and 50% Corning Glass Works Code 7740 glass (Pyrex). They were constructed by placing a layer of ground glass in the die, followed by a layer of alumina fiber coated with slurry, then a second layer of ground glass, another layer of slurry coated alumina fiber at right angles to the first alumina fiber layer thus forming a 0°, 90° composite. This process is continued to give a total of 60 layers of alumina fiber and 62 layers of glass. The resulting stack is then hot pressed in argon in a graphite die at a pressure of 2000 psi and a temperature of 1120°C for a time of 1 hr. In Figure 17 a cross section of a scrap edge of such a sample is shown at low magnification. The biaxial character of the composite is readily noticed as well as a high and uniform fiber distribution and the almost total absence of all porosity.

These medium temperature biaxial composites of alumina fiber in Pyrex glass were used only to work out the variables in the process for making such samples. All subsequent biaxial specimens were prepared from a distribution of approximately 50% DuPont alumina fiber, Type FP, in a matrix of fused silica diluted by a 5% C.G.W. 7740 (Pyrex) glass addition. This 5% of lower melting glass is intentionally added both to inhibit devitrification of the fused silica and to form a liquid sintering aid. Composites of this type could be prepared by hot pressing at temperatures of 1344 to 1366°C at a pressure of 2000 psi held for 1 hr and either a vacuum or argon atmosphere. In contrast to the work on graphite fiber reinforced glass composites reported in the previous paper (2), the pressure must be released while the sample is still at its highest temperature to avoid cracked samples since the alumina fiber has a much higher coefficient of thermal expansion than the glass. The alumina fiber reinforced fused silica samples when sectioned show that the alumina fibers have moved greater distances than is the case for the alumina fiber reinforced Pyrex glass matrices and are more likely to have some porosity.

Biaxial samples of alumina fiber reinforced fused silica (with 5% Pyrex dilution) were submitted to the Dynatech Corporation for thermal conductivity measurements. The results of these measurements are shown in Figure 18. As

Fig. 17 - Cross Section of Biaxial Specimen of DuPont Alumina Fiber FP in C.G.W. 7740 Glass

Fig. 18 - Thermal Conductivity of FP Fiber-Pyrex Glass Matrix

shown in this figure it is evident that the addition of the alumina fibers to the fused silica matrix gives only a slight increase in the thermal conductivity of the fused silica presumably because each alumina fiber is isolated by the coating of fused silica, which surrounds it. The alumina fiber reinforced fused silica composite, therefore, has a markedly lower thermal conductivity than other common refractories including alumina.

The thermal expansion of the alumina fiber reinforced fused silica composite (with 5% Pyrex dilution) was also measured as a function of temperature. The results of these measurements are shown in Figure 19. The long linear portion of Figure 19 is as expected but the nonlinear S shaped portion of the curve between 150°C and 350°C probably indicates a displacive transformation due to the formation of a second phase at the high temperatures of the hot pressing operation. The amount of this second phase present is as yet unknown but X-ray studies identify it as arising from a transformation of part of the fused silica to cristobalite and high cristobalite is known to undergo a displacive transformation to low cristobalite on cooling in the temperature range of 200 to 275°C.

The techniques of forming alumina fiber reinforced fused silica (diluted with 5% Pyrex) glass matrix just described can also be used successfully to form curved samples. In Figure 20 a biaxial sample in shape of a spherical segment of a 20 cm diameter sphere is shown. It has a thickness of 0.32 cm and was readily formable by the usual hot pressing die properly shaped without any problem.

Fig. 19 - Thermal Expansion of FP Fiber-Pyrex Matrix

Fig. 20 - Curved Samples of Al_2O_3 Fiber Reinforced Silica Composites

Relative Position of Alumina Fiber Reinforced Glass Matrix Composites

As stated in the introduction the best of those composites such as a carbon or boron or glass fiber reinforced organic matrix composite is limited in use to temperatures below 300°C and the substitution of an aluminum alloy for the matrix improves this upper temperature of use only slightly. In Figure 21, the relative position of the new alumina fiber reinforced silica matrix compositions with respect to temperature compared to other composites currently available is shown.

Conclusions

An all ceramic composite system comprised of high strength alumina fibers in a glass matrix has been described. The concept for this type of composite arose from the recent availability of alumina fiber in tow form from DuPont Corporation. Calculations of the microstresses in the alumina fiber reinforced glass matrix composite as the composite is thermally cycled indicated that the structural integrity of the composite would be maintained even after repeated heating to temperatures of 1000°C or higher for alumina fibers in a silica matrix. After considering several methods of generating such an alumina fiber-glass matrix composite, a slurry method followed by hot pressing was adapted.

The alumina fiber-silica matrix composite which resulted is characterized by a use temperature in excess of 1000°C or 1832°F, fine environmental stability, excellent thermal shock resistance, low dielectric constant and loss tangent, a coefficient of thermal expansion similar to borosilicate glasses, low thermal conductivity, and a flexural strength about the same as that of sintered alumina or six times that of impregnated slip-cast fused silica. This material can be made as either uniaxially or multiaxially reinforced hot pressed blocks. But this material, i.e. alumina fiber reinforced fused silica, is far from fully characterized and much more research is needed particularly on increasing the strength of the composite if possible and on alternate methods of producing the composite which are cheaper and allow the making of larger shapes.

Fig. 21 - Relative Position of FP Al₂O₃ Fiber Reinforced Composites

Acknowledgements

Figures 2, 4 and 5 are the property of DuPont Corporation. Permission for their use was granted UTRC by Drs. Ashok K. Dingra and Allen Champion.

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